

Impact of Detailed Depletion Chains and Cross-Section Treatments on Nuclide Inventory using SWAT-X

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the impact of detailed depletion-chain and cross-section treatments on burnup calculation results using SWAT-X, which is a Monte Carlo burnup code currently under development by the authors. In this work, a new capability to construct arbitrary depletion chains based on ENDF-6 formatted nuclear data libraries has been implemented in SWAT-X. Detailed depletion chains consisting of 4,070 nuclides were constructed using decay and fission yield data from JENDL-5. Using these depletion chains, burnup calculations for a UO₂ pin-cell model assuming a PWR were performed with different cross-section treatments. Cross sections for 226 major nuclides were treated in continuous energy in the Monte Carlo calculations for all cases, whereas those for the remaining nuclides in the depletion chain were treated differently, either in continuous energy or multi group with different structures, to evaluate their impact on the calculated nuclide inventories. The results indicate that the effect of the cross-section treatment is small, suggesting that a simplified approach with multi-group cross sections is sufficient. In this study, the impact of cross-section coverage in the depletion chain was also examined by extending the data to include a total of 2,697 nuclides using TENDL-2023. As a result, some changes and new generations of nuclides were observed, although their overall impact on the nuclide inventory was limited.

Keywords: burnup calculation, SWAT-X, depletion chain, nuclide inventory

1. INTRODUCTION

Burnup calculations predict nuclide compositions and related characteristics, such as radiation sources and decay heat, in spent fuels. It plays a crucial role in the safety assessment of spent fuel. In burnup calculations, accurate tracking of nuclear reactions and nuclide decay during irradiation relies critically on nuclear data, such as cross sections, fission yields, and decay data. Efforts to evaluate and expand nuclear data libraries have been actively continued, providing increasingly comprehensive datasets. For example, JENDL-3.3 [1] released in 2002 contains neutron reaction data for 337 nuclides, while the number of nuclides increased to 406 nuclides in JENDL-4.0 (2010) [2] and further to 795 nuclides in JENDL-5 (2021) [3]. Similarly, decay data coverage expanded from 3,237 nuclides in the JENDL Decay Data File 2015 [4] to 4,070 nuclides in the decay data sublibrary of JENDL-5. TENDL-2023 [5], which currently covers the widest range of nuclides, contains neutron reaction data for 2,847 nuclides.

In burnup calculations, nuclear data are organized into depletion chains, which define the set of nuclides, the reactions, and decay paths considered in the calculation. The size of a depletion chain directly affects computational cost, and it is therefore common to use simplified chains according to the calculation purpose. For example, the depletion chain used in ORIGEN2 [6] includes over 1,000 nuclides, making it a relatively large chain suitable for a wide range of applications, such as activation and radioactive source calculations. In contrast, CHAINJ40 [7], a depletion-chain dataset based on JENDL-4.0 available in MVP-BURN [8], includes only 226 nuclides. It primarily focuses on reactor physics calculations and only considers nuclides that have a large impact on neutronics calculations to reduce the computational time. Advances in computational performance now make it feasible to employ

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detailed depletion chains without simplification. The use of such detailed chains enables a more precise and comprehensive understanding of the characteristics of spent fuel, potentially revealing insights that were previously overlooked.

We are currently developing the burnup calculation code system SWAT-X [9]. In its development, particular emphasis has been placed on enabling burnup calculations with detailed depletion chains. In this study, SWAT-X was extended to allow the construction of detailed depletion chains based on evaluated nuclear data libraries, and the extended system was applied to burnup calculations for a UO_2 fuel pin-cell model assuming a PWR. The impact of employing detailed depletion chains on evaluated nuclide inventories was then examined, with particular emphasis on cross-section treatments. Specifically, we investigated the effect of (1) the energy resolution of cross sections (continuous, multi-group) and (2) the coverage of cross sections (the number of nuclides for which multi-group cross sections are provided) on the calculation results.

2. DEPLETION CHAIN CONSTRUCTION IN SWAT-X

SWAT-X is a Monte Carlo burnup calculation code system currently under development in JAEA. SWAT-X employs CRAMO [10] as the burnup solver, while neutron transport in burnup calculations is performed using MVP3 [8], a continuous-energy Monte Carlo code. CRAMO is a one-point burnup calculation code based on the Chebyshev Rational Approximation Method (CRAM) [11]. It utilizes ORLIBJ40 [12], which is a compilation of nuclear data libraries for ORIGEN2 mainly based on JENDL-4.0. Thus, the depletion chain and cross sections used in SWAT-X were based on ORLIBJ40, except for cross sections for nuclides explicitly treated in MVP3 transport calculations, in which JENDL-5 or other libraries could be used.

In this study, to enable burnup calculations with a detailed depletion chain fully based on JENDL-5 or other latest libraries, we developed a depletion-chain construction capability for SWAT-X. Figure 1 illustrates the calculation flow in SWAT-X, including this capability. In this procedure, SWAT-X reads ENDF-6 [13] formatted files for decay data and neutron-induced or spontaneous fission yields to construct a detailed depletion chain, in which all nuclides included in the decay data are considered. Neutron reaction paths are incorporated into the chain using the SWAT-X library, a cross-section library generated by processing ENDF-6 formatted neutron cross-section data with FRENDY v2 [14]. This library provides multi-group, infinitely diluted cross sections for reactions such as $(n, 2n)$, $(n, 3n)$, $(n, \text{fission})$, (n, γ) , (n, p) , (n, d) , (n, t) , $(n, {}^3\text{He})$, and (n, α) , corresponding to MT numbers 16–18 and 102–107 in the ENDF-6 format, at representative temperatures (300 K, 600 K, 900 K, 1200 K, etc.).

The SWAT-X library is also employed to prepare one-group cross sections for nuclides and reactions that are not explicitly treated in MVP3 calculations. In MVP3, only user-specified nuclides are included in the irradiated fuel composition to reduce memory requirements. One-group cross sections for these nuclides are calculated for the $(n, \text{fission})$, $(n, 2n)$, and capture reactions. The $(n, \text{fission})$ and $(n, 2n)$ cross sections obtained from MVP3 are directly used. The capture cross sections in MVP3 correspond to the sum of all absorption cross sections except for $(n, \text{fission})$, and therefore do not directly represent the (n, γ) reaction. These capture cross sections are used to correct the corresponding cross sections calculated from the SWAT-X library. The neutron spectrum (multi-group flux) in the fuel region, obtained from MVP3, is used to collapse the multi-group cross sections in the SWAT-X library with linear interpolation with respect to fuel temperature. The resulting one-group cross sections for MT numbers 102–107 are uniformly adjusted so that their sum matches the one-group capture cross section calculated by MVP3. For nuclides and reactions not considered in MVP3, one-group cross sections are similarly derived using the neutron spectrum from MVP3 in combination with the SWAT-X library. The energy group structure used in the SWAT-X library must be consistent with that of the multi-group flux calculated by MVP3. In this study, two energy group structures (172-group and 361-group) were employed to investigate the impact of the energy group structure on the burnup calculation.

In SWAT-X, the one-group cross sections derived from its library inherently include errors associated with the use of a multi-group energy structure and the absence of resonance treatment, in contrast to the continuous-energy-based cross sections used in MVP3. Nuclides in the depletion chain that lack cross-section data are assumed to be non-reactive (zero cross section). For example, when only JENDL-5 is employed, approximately 3,300 nuclides are treated as non-reactive. In this study, we investigate

the influence of these factors, namely the treatment of energy dependence in cross sections and the cross-section coverage of nuclides in depletion chains, on the calculated nuclide inventories.

SWAT-X is capable of applying the predictor–corrector method. In this method, the one-group cross sections obtained from both MVP3 and the SWAT-X library are averaged between the predictor and corrector steps. The burnup calculation in the corrector step is then performed using these averaged cross sections to update nuclide compositions for the subsequent burnup step.

Figure 1. Calculation flow in SWAT-X incorporating the depletion-chain construction capability.

3. NUMERICAL RESULTS

Burnup calculations using SWAT-X with its depletion-chain construction capability were performed for a UO₂ fuel pin-cell model. The model specifications were adopted from the benchmark for next-generation LWR fuels [15]. The enrichment of U-235 was 6.5 wt%. The linear power density was set to 0.179 kW/cm, and the burnup steps were 0.0, 0.1, 1.0, 2.5, 5.0, ..., and 60.0 GWd/t. In the MVP3 calculations, the number of neutron histories per cycle, effective cycles, and discarded cycles were 10,000, 1,000, and 100, respectively. The predictor–corrector method was applied to all burnup calculations conducted in this study.

For the nuclear data, decay data and fission yields were taken from JENDL-5. Consequently, the depletion chains used in all calculations in this study consist of 4,070 nuclides. Regarding the treatment of cross sections, four cases summarized in Table I were compared.

With respect to the nuclides treated in MVP3 calculations, cases A and D included all 795 nuclides in JENDL-5 for cross-section evaluation, whereas cases B and C considered 226 nuclides. The 226 nuclides used in cases B and C were selected from ChainJ40. Concerning the energy-group structure employed in the SWAT-X library, cases A, B, and D adopted the XMAS 172-group structure [16], while case C utilized the SHEM 361-group structure [17]. It should be noted that the SWAT-X library was also used in case A to calculate one-group ($n, 3n$) cross sections and to correct cross sections for MT = 102–107, because MVP3 provides one-group cross sections only for ($n, \text{fission}$), ($n, 2n$), and capture (assumed as the sum of MT = 102–107) in SWAT-X. The nuclear data source for cases A, B, and C was JENDL-5, meaning that the SWAT-X libraries for these cases comprised the 795 nuclides.

In case D, the SWAT-X library was constructed primarily from JENDL-5 for the 795 nuclides and supplemented with data from TENDL-2023 for the remaining nuclides. All nuclides in TENDL-2023 were included, except for those absent from the depletion chain based on JENDL-5 decay data, resulting in a total of 2,697 nuclides in the SWAT-X library. Note that the (n, γ) reaction of O-15 evaluated in TENDL-2023 was excluded from the depletion chain because anomalous results were observed in the case D calculations, which were mitigated by removing this reaction. Although the cause of the anomaly remains unclear, it is possible that the cyclic connection of the depletion chain via the (n, γ) reaction of O-15 adversely affected the calculation results.

Table I. Summary of calculation cases with different cross-section treatments.

Case	Number of nuclides treated in MVP3 calculations (Continuous energy cross sections)	Number of nuclides treated in multi-group cross section	Energy group structure in SWAT-X library	Nuclear data source of SWAT-X library
A	795	0	XMAS172	JENDL-5 (795 nuclides)
B	226	569 (= 795 – 226)	XMAS172	JENDL-5 (795 nuclides)
C	226	569 (= 795 – 226)	SHEM361	JENDL-5 (795 nuclides)
D	795	1902 (= 2697 – 795)	XMAS172	JENDL-5 (795 nuclides) + TENDL-2023 (1902 nuclides)

Figure 2 compares the nuclide number densities at 60 GWd/t between cases A and B (left figure) and between cases B and C (right figure). The comparison between cases A and B investigates the impact of applying continuous-energy treatment to the cross sections of a subset of nuclides on the burnup

calculation, whereas the comparison between cases B and C examines the effect of employing a finer energy-group structure for those nuclides. The relative differences shown on the vertical axes in Figure 2 are given in absolute values. In this analysis, only nuclides with number densities greater than 1×10^{-16} (1/barn/cm) were considered.

The nuclides in Figure 2 are categorized into three groups:

- 1) 226 nuclides whose cross sections are treated with continuous energy in all cases,
- 2) 795 nuclides except for nuclides in group 1) whose cross sections are treated with continuous energy in case A but with group-wise structures in cases B and C, and
- 3) 4,070 nuclides except for nuclides in groups 1) and 2) that have no cross-section data.

Figure 2 shows that the distributions of relative differences are quite similar between the two comparisons. Nuclides with large number densities primarily belong to group 1). Nuclides in groups 2) and 3) are generally distributed at lower number densities, although some exhibit relatively higher values. The relative differences tend to be small for nuclides with large number densities, for example, less than 1% for nuclides with number densities above 1×10^{-10} . These results indicate that the detailed treatment of the energy dependence of cross section has little impact on the overall nuclide inventory. This finding suggests that the conditions employed in case B are sufficient for demonstrating the basic calculation capability of SWAT-X.

Figure 2. Comparison of nuclide number densities at 60 GWd/t (left: case A vs. case B; right: case B vs. case C).

The relative differences observed for group 2) nuclides are generally larger than those for group 3). This is likely because the nuclides in group 2), which have cross sections, are more sensitive to differences in the energy treatment of cross sections and to statistical error in the neutron flux distribution evaluated by MVP3. To clarify the impact of statistical uncertainty on the relative differences shown in Figure 2, calculations for case B were repeated ten times with different initial random seeds in MVP3. Figure 3 presents the relative standard deviations of these ten results with respect to the nominal values in case A. A comparison between Figures 2 and 3 shows that the distributions are very similar, indicating that statistical uncertainty is the dominant source of the differences among cases A, B, and C.

Focusing on the distribution of group 3) in Figure 2, the relative differences between cases A and B are slightly smaller than those between cases B and C. This is likely because cases A and B employ the same energy-group structure (XMAS172), and thus the effects of cross-section treatment on the nuclides in group 3), which are mediated through their parent nuclides with cross sections, are more similar between these two cases.

Consequently, the differences in nuclide inventories among cases A, B, and C are small, and their effects on k_{eff} values are negligible. In this study, the k_{eff} values in all cases (including case D) remained within approximately $\pm 0.05\%$ at all burnup steps, which corresponds to the three-sigma statistical uncertainty of the k_{eff} values evaluated from the ten repeated calculations of case B.

Figure 3. Statistical error of nuclide number densities at 60 GWd/t in case B.

Figure 4 compares nuclide inventories between cases A and D, in order to investigate the impact of coverage of nuclides with cross sections in the depletion chain. Unlike Figure 2, which presents the relative differences, Figure 4 displays the number densities in case D plotted against those in case A. The nuclides in Figure 4 are categorized into three groups in the same manner as in Figure 2.

Figure 4. Comparison of nuclide number densities at 60 GWd/t between case A and case D.

According to Figure 4, the number densities of most nuclides correspond closely between cases A and D. However, some nuclides in case D exhibit higher values, likely due to the inclusion of additional cross sections from TENDL-2023. Among these nuclides, the highest number density observed in case D is 2.0×10^{-10} for Pu-244, which appears to result from the addition of a reaction pathway via the (n, γ) reaction of Pu-243. As shown in Figure 4, noticeable differences are also observed for several other heavy nuclides. Nevertheless, the number densities of these nuclides, including that of Pu-244, are relatively small compared with those of the major nuclides typically considered in spent fuel inventories.

The inclusion of the TENDL-2023 cross sections also resulted in the generation of 243 nuclides whose number densities were zero in case A. These nuclides are plotted at zero on the horizontal axis in Figure 4. The maximum number density among these newly generated nuclides is 4.8×10^{-19} , indicating that the impact of adding TENDL-2023 data on previously unevaluated nuclides is small.

4. CONCLUSION

The impact of detailed depletion chains and cross section treatments on the calculated nuclide inventory was investigated using a Monte Carlo burnup code SWAT-X. The depletion chain was constructed based on JENDL-5, comprising 4,070 nuclides. Cross sections for 226 major nuclides were treated with continuous-energy data in the MVP3 neutron transport calculations, while the remaining nuclides with JENDL-5 data were treated in different ways, either with continuous-energy or multi-group structures, to assess their impact on burnup calculation results. The results showed that the differences in cross-section treatment for minor nuclides had only a small impact on the calculated nuclide inventory, indicating that the simplified condition used in case C, where 226 nuclides are considered in MVP3 and the others are treated with the XMAS-172 energy group structure in the SWAT-X library, is sufficient for practical burnup calculations. The impact of cross-section coverage in the depletion chain was also examined by supplementing JENDL-5 data with TENDL-2023. Although some changes in nuclide inventories were observed, particularly among heavy nuclides, their absolute inventories were small. This finding suggests that the effect of extended cross-section coverage on the overall nuclide inventory is small.

As future work, the impact of these modeling choices on other characteristics, such as radioactivity and decay heat, will be investigated.

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